

Incidence of Home Accidents and the Prevalence of Burns and Fractures among Geriatric Patients in Selected Public Hospitals in Southwest Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15874538>

Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the incidence of home accidents and to quantify the prevalence of burns and fractures in geriatric patients. A cross-sectional analysis was conducted on geriatric patients aged 65 years and older who were admitted due to home-related accidents. Participants were selected through stratified random sampling from selected public hospitals in Southwest Nigeria. A sample of 134 participants was randomly selected for the study using the minimum sample size formula developed by Cochran as determinant. Data were collected on demographics, prevalence and knowledge of the causes and preventive strategies of home accidents. Inferential statistics were employed, specifically Independent t-test, to determine the strength and direction of associations. There is relatively high knowledge of causes and preventive strategies of home accident burns and fractures, yet many respondents still lacks some appropriate home modifications that can enhance quality safety life. There is a statistically significant difference in the prevalence of home accident burns and fractures between male and female geriatric patients. Also, there is a statistical significant relationship between knowledge of the causes of home accident and preventive strategies ($r = .619$, $n = 25$, $p(.001) < .05$). The study recommends implementing regular home safety evaluations for older adults to identify potential hazards and recommend modifications.

Keywords: Home Accidents, Geriatric patients, Burns, Fractures, Injury Prevalence, Elderly Care